

Modelling & Design System of PID & LQR Controller for Inverted Pendulum

(Pemodelan & Rekaan Sistem Kawalan PID & LQR untuk Bandul Songsang)

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this project is to run simulation and do some comparison between inverted pendulum system that use different types of controller. The aim is to decide which controller gives the best performance to maintaining the pendulum in vertical position regarding the pendulum's angle. It is a challenging problem because it always in uncontrolled and unstable state. Two controllers were chosen which is Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) and Linear-Quadratic-Regulator (LQR) controller to control the linearized system of inverted pendulum model. Matlab/Simulink were used to run the simulation for both controllers, and the results show that both controllers have the capability to control the angle of the pendulum. The results show that PID controller give a better the best performance compared to LQR and is illustrated in form of graph and table.

Keywords: Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID); Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR); Inverted Pendulum System

ABSTRAK

Tujuan utama penulisan ini adalah untuk menjalankan simulasi dan membuat perbandingan di antara bandul songsang yang menggunakan jenis kawalan yang berbeza. Ini bertujuan untuk menentukan pengawal yang memberikan prestasi yang terbaik dalam menstabilkan bandul dalam keadaan tegak dengan mengambil kira sudut bandul. Bandul songsang adalah masalah kawalan yang mencabar kerana sentiasa dalam keadaan tidak terkawal dan tidak stabil. Dua pengawal dipilih iaitu pengawal Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) dan pengawal Linear-Quadratic-Regulator (LQR) untuk mengawal model sistem lurus bandul songsang. Matlab dan Simulink digunakan untuk menjalankan simulasi bagi kedua-dua pengawal dan keputusan menunjukkan kedua-dua pengawal mempunyai kebolehan untuk mengawal sudut bandul. Hasil simulasi menunjukkan bahawa pengawal PID memberikan tindak balas yang lebih baik berbanding kawalan LQR dan diterjemahkan di dalam bentuk graf dan jadual.

Kata Kunci: Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID); Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR); Inverted Pendulum System

INTRODUCTION

One of the nonlinear problem is an inverted pendulum system, that many researchers have been considered (Valluru & Singh 2017), most of which have used linearization theory in their control schemes. Regulation of inverted pendulum by classical methods is usually a difficult job (Polekhin 2018).

Since the characteristics of inverted pendulum system is marginally stable, it is used by control engineers to verify other control theory. Inverted pendulum is popular known in aerospace field for model of attitude control. However, it is also have some limitations which is open-loop unstable system and highly non-linear (Barya et al. 2010). Due to no controller exists that can linearize

the system's non-linear dynamics, the pendulum will fall easily, and it makes the modelling become more difficult (Ünal et al. 2012).

The popular control that have been used to overcome this type of problem is LQR control and PID control which is required to have deep study about the system so that in can be tuned and results in the best performance. However, it is quite impossible to specify an accurate mathematical modelling of the system (Tayfun & Servet 2019).

This paper presents the study of performance comparison between PID control and LQR control for inverted pendulum system. The dynamic model and design parameter have been derived and calculated. Performance of each control was investigated and analyzed in controlling the

pendulum's angle. Comparative evaluation between both controllers also presented and discussed.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Inverted pendulum system is quite challenging in control because it is always in uncontrolled state and always need to be stabilize so that it keeps in vertical position (upright).

Unstable open loop and non-linear system is one of the characteristics that can be found in inverted pendulum system. Therefore, the pendulum needs to combined with a controller so that it can be stabilized. To obtain a stable system, control theory is needed. The principle and theory behind the inverted pendulum system need to be understand well in order to get the controlled model of inverted pendulum.

Some of the controller used are PID and LQR controller. Each controller needs a deep knowledge about the system that are going to be controlled. Accurate tuning also needed so that it can give the best response performance. But, the accurate mathematical model for the system quite impossible to be identify and it is involving a very complex differential equation (Tayfun & Servet 2019).

To control the inverted pendulum system, the dynamic movement of the inverted pendulum need to be linearized first. Matlab/Simulink software can simulate the model of the inverted pendulum. (Ahmad Nor Kasruddin bin Nasir 2007).

METHODOLOGY

Mathematical Modelling of Inverted Pendulum

This section will briefly explain on the modelling, which is required before starting the simulation for both types of control. The system has a pendulum rod where one sided of the pendulum were attached on a cart that can move freely in horizontal direction as shown in Figure 1. Few assumptions were made in order to get the dynamical modelling of the system:

- i. The system's initial condition is assumed to be zero, which is in equilibrium state.
- ii. There is only small deviation produced by pendulum's angle to fulfill the linear model.
- iii. Step input applied as an input signal.

FIGURE 1. Schematic diagram of an inverted pendulum

The system's parameter is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Parameter of the physical inverted pendulum system

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Unit
M	Mass of the cart	5	kg
m	Mass of the pendulum	1	kg
d	Friction of the cart	1	N/m/s
l	Length of the pendulum	2	m
I	Inertia of the pendulum	0.006	kgm ²
g	Gravity	-10	m/s ²

From Figure 1, the dynamic equation in horizontal direction and vertical direction were obtained.

$$(M + m)\ddot{x} + d\dot{x} + ml\ddot{\theta}\cos\theta - ml\dot{\theta}^2\sin\theta = F \quad (1)$$

$$(I + ml^2)\ddot{\theta} + mgl\sin\theta = -ml\ddot{x}\cos\theta \quad (2)$$

In upright position or in a stabilize state, $\theta = \pi$ and $\cos\theta = -1$, $\sin\theta = -\varphi$. Those value then substituted into equation (1) and equation (2), and the equation of motion will be obtained as shown below.

$$(I + ml^2)\ddot{\varphi} - mgl\varphi = ml\ddot{x} \quad (3)$$

$$(M + m)\ddot{x} + d\dot{x} - ml\ddot{\varphi} = u \quad (4)$$

The open-loop transfer function of pendulum's angle was obtained by manipulating and rearrange equations (3) and (4). Then, the transfer function was obtained as shown in equation (5) after the substitution of system's parameter.

$$P_{pend}(s) = \frac{0.09982s}{s^3 + 0.1999s^2 - 5.989s - 0.9982} \quad (5)$$

The transfer function then converted into state-space form and output equation as shown below.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{x} \\ \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\phi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.1999 & 1.996 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -0.09982 & 5.989 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \dot{x} \\ \phi \\ \dot{\phi} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.1999 \\ 0 \\ 0.09982 \end{bmatrix} u \quad (6)$$

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{x} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u \quad (7)$$

By calculating the open-loop poles using equation (8) and command `obsv` and `ctrb` in Matlab, the stability of the system can be justified,

$$\det(sI - A) \quad (8)$$

where matrix A is obtained from the state space system. By solving equation (8) using Matlab, the open-loop poles can be solved as follows:

$$p_1 = -0.1665, \quad p_2 = -2.4561, \quad p_3 = 2.4317$$

It can be seen from the value of the open-loop poles that the system is unstable, since the pole 2.4317 were on the right-half plane of s-plane. Therefore, a controller must be equipped so that the inverted pendulum system can be stabilized.

PID Controller Design & Simulation

The meaning of PID is Proportional-Integral-Derivative. This controller sends the output back into the system. The output of the system is essentially changing simultaneously with the different or error occurs between setpoint and measured variable. Each gain value in PID controller have their own effects towards the response of the system.

- i. Proportional gain, K_p :
Act as an amplifier. Responsible for process stability in most systems. If this gain too low, system response will be drifted away, but will produce oscillations if too high.
- ii. Integral gain, K_I :
Responsible for driving error to zero (steady state). High value of K_I will produce oscillations and instability.
- iii. Derivative gain, K_D :
Responsible for system response (transient response) in most systems. If the value set too low, sluggish response produced. Too high, will produce oscillation.

The gain in PID controller was tuned using Ziegler Nichols method that has been implemented in PID Tuner in Matlab. All the gain values obtained

after tuning process is $K_p=162675$, $K_I=2252850$ and $K_D=2884$.

FIGURE 2. PID control structure in Simulink

LQR Controller Design & Simulation

The LQR controller is one of the methods used in modern control theory. By using the state space equation, the controller will have more information about the system that needs to be control. Basically, state-space methods quite easy to use even the system have several outputs (Kunhikrishnan et al. 2016). This controller is using full state feedback to stabilize the system. The control structure of the system with LQR controller is shown below.

FIGURE 3. LQR control structure in Simulink

To design this type of controller, we can vary the value of gain K obtained that satisfy the law of the feedback control, $u = -Kx$. This can be settled by playing around with the value of Q and R value where Q is a symmetric positive semidefinite matrix and R is a symmetric positive definite matrix. The tuning process for LQR controller is by changing the non-zero value of i and j elements in m-file code in Matlab that represents. Based on the system performance response, the values of matrix Q , R and K are shown below.

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1000 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R = 0.1$$

$$K = [-100 \quad -122.73 \quad 800.27 \quad 353.68]$$

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

Within this section, the results of the simulation are discussed for both controllers that implemented to the inverted pendulum system. Comparative

evaluation between both controllers also discussed in this section.

Figure 4 graphically illustrates the different response of the system response in controlling the pendulum's angle where unit step was applied as an input signal (reference point). The simulation was run for 10 seconds. In this figure, the graph with blue color is the response of the system using LQR controller while the graph with red color is the response of the system using PID controller. When the PID and LQR controller is applied with a unit step function as an input signal, both systems demonstrate different response in terms of transient and steady state error response. The different characteristics responses for both controllers are given in Table 2.

FIGURE 4. Comparison of system response

Based on Table 2, it can be seen clearly that there is a huge difference between the response of PID and LQR controller. This can be proved by the transient and steady state response which is steady state error, settling time, overshoot, and rising time. PID has the fastest settling time which is 1.3 s while LQR has the slowest settling time which is 3.8 s. Yet, the PID response produced the highest overshoot which is 0.139 because the system response is very fast. Meanwhile, the LQR controller does not produced any overshoot at all due to slower response. Despite of having an overshoot, designed PID controller can make the pendulum in upright (vertical) position due to faster response. Besides, the overshoot produced in PID controller system response are acceptable. From the reference point, it can be seen that the PID controller have a good control can control the angle and deviation of pendulum rather than LQR controller. For the last characteristics, both PID and LQR controller does not have steady state error.

TABLE 2. Summary of the system performance characteristics

Controller	LQR	PID
Rising time	Fast	Slow
Settling time	3.8 s	1.3 s
Maximum overshoot	0	0.139
Steady state error	0	0

From Figure 4, PID controller has the fastest rising time compared to LQR controller. It is

because the LQR controller undergoes minimum phase during the starting point due to zeros at origin in complex plane.

CONCLUSION

This paper successfully designs and simulates two controls which is PID and LQR controller. Based on the results and the analysis, it can be concluded that both control methods can control the angle of the linearized inverted pendulum system. Comparison for each controller was made. The response of the inverted pendulum system with a controller can be seen clearly using Matlab and Simulink software in the form of graph. Simulation results show that PID controller has better performance compared to LQR controller in controlling the inverted pendulum system because it has faster response even there is changes in reference signal. Each controller requires some enhancement. Enhancement needed in LQR controller so that it has faster rising and settling time so that the pendulum can be stabilize quickly. Meanwhile for PID controller can be improved so that the maximum overshoot can be reduced.

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